

Ways to organize supervision of extracurricular and extracurricular activities

Matyoqubova Fotima Urinbayevna

Urganch Davlat Universiteti talabasi

Аннотация: В данной научной статье рассказывается об организации внеурочной деятельности, ее видах, этапах и формах, а также о том, как руководителю следует руководить работниками в этой деятельности.

Ключевые слова: Основные формы внеурочной деятельности, система классных занятий, сборник, понятие, речевой этикет.

Abstract: This scientific article talks about the organization of extracurricular activities, their types, stages and forms, as well as how the leader should lead employees in these activities.

Key words: The main forms of extracurricular activities, class lesson system, collection, concept, speech etiquette.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada sinfdan tashqari ishlarni tashkil qilish, ularning turlari, bosqichlari va shakllari hamda ushbu ishlarda rahbar hodimlarni qanday ish jarayonini olib borishi kerakligi haqida soʻz boradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Sinfdan tashqari ishlarning asosiy shakllari, sinf dars tizimi, kolleksiya toʻplash, konsepsiya, nutq odobi.

Understanding the essence of the educational process, taking the initiative in organizing it, business acumen and dexterity, and the ability to effectively apply all new and advanced things in practice is one of the principles of guiding the process of personal development of a school student. The combination of collective and individual leadership, which is an example of the implementation of an effective leadership style in school life and activities, ensures the fate of children, the

responsibility of the team of pedagogues for their education, and the personal responsibility of the director. Planning shows the director the prospects for the clear implementation of all issues of education. Based on this doctrine, planning extracurricular activities and organizing management and control over their implementation is of great importance in the school's internal management system. Under the leadership of the deputy director for spiritual and educational affairs, class leaders, methodical association, experienced teachers, school library, student-youth organization, students will prepare the general school plan of extracurricular and extracurricular activities it is appropriate to create it with the active participation of the association, the parents' committee and the leaders of the circle, and approve it after discussion at the school meeting.

The director achieves unity in his attitude towards teachers, class leaders, tutors and students, strives for the school's harmonious cooperation with the family, work groups of adults, community organizers. When leading the educational process of the school, the director pays special attention to the consistency of the educational work of elementary and school classes, thereby implementing the principles of continuity of education both during the educational process and outside the classroom work plan is a mandatory pedagogical document. The work plan can be made quarterly, semi-annually and annually. In the present conditions, according to experience, the use of the half-year plan is very effective. If the following are included in the planning, its effectiveness will increase significantly: The plan should be made as appropriate as possible depending on the local conditions, the location of the school, the level and age of the students. The plan should be targeted and realistic. It should be agreed with the association of children and teenagers. The plan should reflect what students will do during the fall, winter, spring and summer vacations. The persons performing the

events, their duration and implementation, and their type should be clearly indicated. The plan must be reviewed by the deputy principals and approved by the principal. Pedagogical training, experience and personal characteristics of the class leader are of great importance in planning. Students' level of knowledge about Eastern national customs and traditions. Encyclopaedic knowledge of intellectuals, thinkers, poets and writers of modern times. It is appropriate to use interview and questionnaire methods to determine the above. Only then, each teacher-educator will come up with unique and unique educational event plans. Such plans have an educational effect and can achieve the intended goal.

Ways to organize supervision of extracurricular and extracurricular activities. It is difficult to achieve the intended goal without clearly planning the educational work in the school, without determining its content, form and methods, without putting it into a certain system. The educational effect of extracurricular activities depends to a large extent on the level of organization of the educational process and how the student group organizes various activities. Extracurricular activities are not limited to the compulsory program, but also bring together different students voluntarily. He carries out work on the basis of their initiative, makes them interested in science, brings them into the environment of the cultural life of the people. Extracurricular activities are the most important factor in the formation of social activity, social consciousness and moral habits in a person. This activity includes the work of the scientific community, literary and school theaters, readers' conferences and discussions on various topics, lectures and conversations on political, moral, scientific-popular and labor topics, socially useful work, political information, holiday evenings and mornings, to includes the necessary exercises. According to its content, students' extracurricular work is a means of thinking and attitude. Because the information received in

extracurricular activities is perceived, processed and new knowledge is created on this basis. Pupils participate in extracurricular activities, get into certain relationships with different people, and face different tasks. That is why the more diverse the extracurricular activities of students, the richer their relationships, the wider the range of relationships and the more effective their spiritual growth. In educational work outside of school, students learn to work in a team, feel the joy of social work, join production work, get used to obeying public opinion, fighting for the honor of the team. Extracurricular activities are determined according to the spiritual and physical development and age characteristics of the participants. This process is also affected by the conditions of the school where they are studying. Although the tasks of all schools in our country are the same, they have their own characteristics, and these characteristics are clearly visible in cultural and national conditions. It is advisable for educators, class leaders to use the following work methods in their educational work outside the classroom and school: Verbal work methods. Various information, meetings, morning gatherings, lectures, readers' conferences, discussions, meetings, newspapers, radio magazines. Practical work methods. Trips to different places, sports competitions, Olympiad, work activities of Iztopars, clubs of young naturalists, sabbaliks.

Demonstration methods of work. School museums, the room of heroes of war and labor, exhibitions of new books. The educational work requires the pedagogue to use all his abilities, to constantly search. Because the future generation should be educated, organized, harmonious, and true citizens of our country. Civic activity means recognizing one's rights and duties before one's country, consciously observing the standards of living and morals set by the society, working and working together. stabilizes activity and moral maturity: responsible for the fate and effectiveness of reforms, a priority state policy maker in the

formation of selfless individuals for the tomorrow and future of our country; political awareness and social activity, that is, understanding of the state's domestic and international policy and perception. Patriotism is the feeling of internationalism, being ready to actively participate in social and political life; the civic duty before the people, the state, that is, knowing the principles of legislation, one's rights and duties before one's homeland, neighborhood, family, and strictly following them. Intolerant attitude to the violation of the legislation. The deputy director of the school's spiritual and educational affairs gives instructions to the relevant pedagogical staff in connection with the tasks specified in the regulations. Based on the scope of his duties, he solves the issues of organizing activities outside the classroom and school and opening new clubs.

Duties of the deputy director:

- approve the work plan of class leaders in cooperation with the director;*
- approve the plan of sports competitions held at the school in cooperation with the director;*
- approval of the plan of various club activities in cooperation with the director.*

Educational activities are conducted on the basis of analysis and discussion of specific facts and events from children's daily life, examples from fiction, contemporary press, and films. The feature of these works is that it teaches children to think about their moral actions and give them the correct assessment. Educational work outside the classroom and school complements and expands the educational process of students in their spare time, creates opportunities for students to learn independently, to increase their positive abilities and initiative. The scope, main directions, and content of the educational work carried out with the class team should correspond to the level of mental development of the students at each stage. Educational work requires the pedagogue to use all his

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abilities, to search tirelessly. Because the future generation should be educated, organized, harmonious, and real citizens of our Motherland. Conducting educational work in elementary grades at school, organizing it, is organized by the head of the class or organizers of educational work. The main directions of educational work: forming the foundations of a scientific worldview in students, educating them in the spirit of national independence; education of students' moral culture, conscious attitude towards their rights and duties; organization of socially useful work of students; is the formation of self-management skills in students. One of the main tasks of a primary school student and class leader is to create a cohesive educational team of students. Elementary team work is built in such a way that it is constantly connected with other teams of the class, common school traditions are preserved. The elementary team participates in the activities of social useful works of the general school under the guidance of the teacher-educator and class leader, student self-management bodies. The teacher and the head of the class, along with forming a healthy, harmonious group of children, support children's constant interests and direct their socially useful activities. Young students are very active and active. The desire for activity is an organic need of children of this age. However, children will not have enough life experience and need daily pedagogical guidance. The primary school teacher chooses methods that provide an excellent opportunity to create real public relations of educational work, educate children to care for each other, and create favorable opportunities for the development of individual abilities. The teacher helps children in primary classes to choose the type of activity that interests them. However, often, young students cannot correctly assess their own characteristics due to age characteristics. The growth of children and the formation of social skills and abilities in them changes the process of the teacher-educator in leading the group of children. The teacher

creates a healthy public opinion based on the creation of a cohesive group of children in primary grades. The work of elementary school teachers in the field of creating a children's educational community is continued by class leaders of upper classes.

The primary school teacher studies students in the natural conditions of education and upbringing, in the process of their team activities. Extracurricular work extends the time of pedagogical impact on students aimed at a certain goal, it allows to expand and deepen the knowledge acquired by the teacher in classes, to develop children's abilities, to satisfy their various interests, and to organize cultural holidays. Extracurricular activities have great potential to engage children in community life. Each community has a self-governing body and is considered an integral part of the national community. It also connects with the national community through unity of purpose and organizational features. Joint activity aimed at meeting the needs of social society is the next important characteristic of the community. It is important that the socio-ideological direction of the team's activity is reflected in the content of the team's activity. Analyzing the process of children's team development, they divide it into the following two stages: Initial consolidation of the team; forming a team and developing each of its members. Formation of a team is important for team members and unique requirements for their activities. The only requirement includes the rules of behavior of students during the course of the lesson, during breaks, during extracurricular activities, in public areas and at home. The regular implementation of the well-thought-out system of requirements ensures the establishment of a certain order in the school. The requirements set by the pedagogues give positive results under the following conditions: Respect for the personality of the student. Consider the circumstances of a particular school or classroom. Clarity of requirements. The requirements for

students' appearance, dress, behavior and behavior must serve to form their spiritual culture. The teacher should not only know the volume and system of demands, but also master the methodology of making demands. The method of setting requirements for students consists of introducing children to the content of requirements, explaining their importance, gaining experience, and regularly monitoring them. Acquaintance of students with the requirements is often carried out in general meetings, where the director of the educational institution or the deputy director of educational affairs introduces the students with the content of the prospective plans and the requirements in the process of their implementation. . In some cases, detailed introduction is carried out in the course of practical demonstration, and later in the class meetings by classes, in the process of organizing special conversations.

Acquaintance of the behavior with the requirements directed to the formation of content should be combined with training on these requirements. Educating behavior is more complicated than educating mind. Students may have a good understanding of the requirements, but in most cases they do not follow them. Therefore, regular practice turns cultural behavior into a habit. In the process of setting requirements, it is necessary to establish control over students' compliance with them. Monitoring is carried out using various conditions, such as keeping a behavior log, recording grades on the stand for class attendance, etc. Control should be real and regular. Students should be informed about its results.

References:

1. A. Mavlonova, .Normurodona. Methodology of educational work. Study guide. Tashkent, "Ian" 2008.
2. R. Mavlonova, N. Rahmonkulova,. Normurodova, K. Matnazarova Methodology of educational works. The textbook was published in TDPU Rizziography named after Nizami. Tashkent, 2014.
3. K. Khoshimov, S. Ochilov. Anthology of Uzbek pedagogy. Educational guide. T: Teacher since 2010
4. R.A. Mavlonova, N.H. Vahidova, N.H. Rakhmonkulova. Theory and history of pedagogy. Textbook T:. Science and technology. 2010
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF-5712 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".